

REINCARNATE

D1.2 – Launch version CP-IM Platform

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D1.2 Launch version CP-IM Platform (Software)

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Abstract

This deliverable reports the Launch version of the Circular Potential Information Platform (CP-IM) which operates as an essential segment of REINCARNATE project. While CP-IM will be created as dynamic integration of several distinct components, the launch version consists of the integration of its two core components, the DMO RE Suite real estate information management platform and the Mainflux open-source IoT Platform. The report describes both platforms, their function within CP-IM as well how to use them in this phase of the project.

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IoT platform, microservices, cloud, user manuals, IoT protocols, real estate management platform

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Acronyms and definitions

Acronym	Meaning
BIM	Building information modelling
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
GUI	Graphic User Interface
CDW	Construction and demolition waste
CP-IM	Circular Potential Information Management platform
CRUD	Create, Read, Update, Delete
DMO	DEMO Consultants
IoT	Internet of Things
MFL	Mainflux Labs
MYMP	Multi-year maintenance plans
mTLS	Mutual TLS authentication
NEN2767	Standard for condition measurement of buildings and their installations
SSO	Single Sign On
TLS	Transport Layer Security

Reincarnate project

The average lifespan of a building is 39 years — in Europe, it is only 25-30 years — and the main reason for demolition is obsolescence. This is why there is a large amount of construction and demolition waste (CDW) — representing approximately 25-30% of all waste in Europe —, in addition to that generated in current construction works.

The recycling rate for CDW is relatively high (above 75%). This activity generated \$126.89 billion in 2019 — Europe contributed the largest share, almost two-fifths of the total global market — and is projected to reach \$149.19 billion by 2027. Unfortunately, many of the most valuable materials in CDW cannot be meaningfully separated and end up in landfills.

This helps to get an idea of the efficiency potential for climate neutrality that exists in construction.

Reincarnate aims at advancing circular economy practices within the European construction industry and enabling to significantly maximise the life cycle of buildings, construction products and materials, reduce CDW by 80%, increase the reusability of buildings, construction products and materials and, as a result, lower the sector's emissions by 70%.

As a result of these actions, Reincarnate will significantly advance circular economy practices within the European construction industry.

First, it will create a Circular Potential Information Management (CP-IM) platform and a set of innovations to use it. These solutions will draw upon emerging digital technologies, such as digital twin representation, artificial intelligence, and robotic automation.

3 empirically proven social science insights will allow fostering widespread adoption of reused high-quality construction products and materials, and business eco-system development frameworks to combine actors within sustainable value chains. All innovations will be demonstrated on eleven selected real-world projects and value chains. Furthermore, business process guidelines and an e-learning platform will be developed to drive the dissemination and exploitation of the Reincarnate results.

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1. Introduction

This deliverable report is part of Work Package (WP) 1 of the REINCARNATE project titled "REINCARNATE CP-IM". The objective of WP1 is a development of Circular Potential Information Management (CP-IM) technologies necessary for the centralization of all information required for the evaluation of a building's potential to avoid construction waste and make the best use of it. An important element of that goal is covered by Task 1.2 "IoT and Digital Twin Platform" and within it the Launch version of CP-IM Platform (Software) which this deliverable addresses.

The circular Potential Information Management (CP-IM) technologies will be created in the form of a complex and dynamic platform that consists of several different integrated instances:

- i) Distributed data system created within the WP1
- ii) Mainflux - Open-source IoT Platform (MFL)
- iii) RE Suite - Real estate information management platform (DMO)
- iv) Reincarnate Digital Twin (MFL + DMO)
- v) Circular Potential Prediction Module created within the WP1
- vi) Circular Value Flow Planning Module

1.1 Purpose of the document and audience

The intended audience for this report is REINCARNATE project partners who need secure IoT data collection from multiple sources and visualization of this data in standard 3D and BIM formats. This document will provide an explanation of the Mainflux open-source IoT platform and building management platform Re-Suite with instructions on how to use them within the initial phase of the project.

1.2 Outline of the report

This document is organized into 4 distinct sections. Section 2 presents the role of CP-IM in REINCARNATE project, an explanation of different instances that will constitute the CP-IM platform and their specific function in it. Section 3 explains in more detail the core components of CP-IM, RE Suite real estate management platform and Mainflux open-source IoT Platform, its features, and instructions on how to use them in this phase of the project. Section 4 outlines the launch version of CP-IM as the integration of RE Suite and Mainflux, as well as the architecture and details of this integration. Finally, section 5 describes future phases of development.

2. CP-IM Platform

The overall objective of the REINCARNATE project is to create technical, commercial, and social instruments within the real estate and construction sector which will enable the extension of the lifetime of building products, elements and materials and foster their reuse in other projects and settings.

CP-IM is the essential segment of the REINCARNATE project whose function is to provide the centralization of all necessary information and data needed for the evaluation of elements at all systemic levels of a building for the avoidance of construction waste and the best reuse of it. In this regard, it will be created as the dynamic integration of several distinct technologies outlined below:

i) Distributed database created on ontologies that describe above mentioned systemic levels of building, i.e., building products, elements, and materials, as well as ontologies for calculating the carbon footprint of these elements

ii) Mainflux Open-source IoT Platform that will serve as a digital foundation for secure IoT data collection and processing, tracing construction components and materials through their life cycle and different use cycles and REINCARNATE Digital Twin Platform which will provide a database of digital replicas of real-world objects.

iii) DMO Real estate information management platform - RE Suite with many functionalities including data collection, real estate and assets control and management, maintenance, graphical 3D visualization, building elements inventories, querying, and filtering as well as interoperability with existing BIM solutions via IFC.

iv) REINCARNATE Digital Twin platform that will be created as integration between RE Suite and Mainflux IoT Platform.

v) Circular Potential Prediction Module that will facilitate lifecycle-based assessment methods for buildings, construction products, and materials with computer vision and deep learning technologies

vi) Circular Value Flow Planning Module that will enable planning regional and cross-regional circular value chains by establishing connections between the BIM models and planning tools and the existing product lifecycle management (PLM), enterprise

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resource planning (ERP), and customer relationship management (CRM) systems of waste management companies (RAS), construction product and material suppliers (LAF), and contractors (MOS, VIAS).

Figure 1: CP-IM Platform

Reincarnate project also conceived a set of technical and process innovations that will leverage the CP-IM platform and combined it with a holistic approach for achieving waste avoidance and circular reuse. The innovation disposition of the whole concept, in which the CP-IM platform is at the center technical and process innovations is depicted in the following diagram.

Figure 2: CP-IM platform and process innovations

The platform can be accessed via <https://demo.demobv.nl/> (credentials are available on request). Upon the entry, access to the main two applications is provided: ReSuite and Mainflux as shown in Figure 3. The two applications will work together to accommodate the needs of the project and embed the innovations that will be developed during the project.

Figure 3: CP-IM platform entry page

3. Existing Systems

3.1. RE Suite

The RE Suite (short for Real Estate Suite) is a real estate information management platform. It assists real estate owners, managers and users with and through collecting, structuring, analysing and disclosing information. The RE Suite consists of various modules, targeting both buildings and civil infrastructure throughout the entire real estate life cycle, from inception to end. Through configuration of these modules the RE Suite can be tailored to various problem domains and support a broad variety of workflows and end user needs.

The RE Suite is a cloud application, accessible through all browsers via <https://demo.demobv.nl>. Credentials are available on request. To support on-site workflows, the RE Suite is supported by an iPad app: RE OnSite. This app is available from the Apple AppStore.

3.1.1 RE Suite in CP-IM

For the REINCARNATE project, the RE Suite is configured as a graphical user interface of the CP-IM and configured with the following modules:

- RE Maintenance
- RE IoT
- RE BIM
- RE Report

RE SUITE

Figure 4: RE Suite Application Navigator

The launch version of the CP-IM RE Suite functions as its main graphical user interface for interaction with real estate objects. Within this user interface, RE Maintenance allows for management of a real estate portfolio as well as dedicated data collection by inspectors. With the addition of the mobile app RE OnSite, this data collection can actually be executed on-site. In the CP-IM this is useful to gather data, register and manage circular potential of building elements.

RE Report allows users to report on circular potential in human readable documents, or export information in machine-readable formats for external analysis or use in other external workflows.

RE BIM enables use of BIM-models, to view and interact with a 3D rendering of a building and analyse various element, product, and material properties for circular potential.

RE IoT connects directly to sensors and actuators in real estate objects. This is the most direct way to gather data, to use to determine circular potential of materials and products in the building.

3.1.2 Graphical User Interface

All modules within the RE Suite have the same setup. On the left-hand side, a vertical blue bar shows the name of the currently active module on top. Clicking this allows a user to switch to another module. Below the button is a list of processes within process groups, ordered to follow a recommended workflow within the current module. The vertical blue bar is as such named the process navigator.

Directly to the right of the process navigator is a vertical white bar called the object navigator. The object navigator lists and allows a user to select current objects. The objects on display are relevant to the currently selected process. For example, when managing a building portfolio, the object navigator will display a list of buildings. When managing sensors, the object navigator will display a list of sensors. The object navigator allows for complex filtering and sorting of its content.

To the right of the object navigator is the working area. Its content and makeup are dependent on the selected process and object(s). At the top, a title shows information on the currently selected object or operation. Below one or more panels or tables display information and allow for interaction. The top panel may also have several tabs to switch to more working areas within the current process. Panels are read-only by default, but some allow for interaction through the buttons in the top-right corner. The plus button adds a record, the trash icon deletes a record, and the pencil enables editing of the current record. Other buttons may become available depending on the selected process, object, and tab. If the button icon does not immediately clarify its purpose, hovering the mouse cursor over the button displays a tooltip with more information.

Most visualisations are fully draggable, sortable, and can be filtered according to user preferences. This allows for powerful information structuring in place. Moving the mouse to the bottom-right corner of the RE Suite unhides a zoom control to support such workflows.

The bottom of the process navigator displays the name of the current user. By clicking this, a user can move to change their account settings or choose to log out

Figure 5: RE Suite process navigator (1), object navigator (2) and working area (3)

3.1.3 RE Maintenance

RE Maintenance supports a full building manager workflow, from portfolio management, through inspection and condition assessment compliant with NEN2767 onto creation of multi-year maintenance plans (MYMP).

Stock

The process group stock allows for portfolio management. The objects process allows a user to manage the population of real estate objects in the RE Suite. Most tabs within this process allow for data entry through the available editable attributes. Two tabs, however, stand out.

Firstly, the Documents tab unlocks a full document management system. Clicking this tab changes the display of the object navigator to a tree of currently available documents for the current object. Clicking a document opens a preview in the working area. Using right-mouse click in the document tree a user can upload new documents or open the document library in a full web interface for easy management and interaction.

Secondly, the BIM-tab unlocks a BIM-viewer, displaying the currently linked BIM-model for this object. For more information on the BIM viewer see module RE BIM.

The GIS process within the Stock group allows for visualisation of the object population on an interactive map. Through the sort and filtering enabled by the object navigator this allows for geographical analysis of (subsets of) the object population. The GIS module also supports various Esri maps and their feature layers. As such the geographical stock of objects can be combined with data from external sources.

Version management

As data evolves and inspections are repeated over the years a history of data builds. The version management process allows a user insight into and management of the various extant datasets.

Survey planning

Condition assessment requires an on-site inspection of a building. Such surveys can however be subject to various conditions, depending on building user, manager and owner needs and wants. Managing multiple surveys for multiple inspectors requires an organisational tool. In this process group distinct types of surveys can be defined and applied and assigned to users. This automatically prepares surveys for inspectors and notifies them of changes in their workload.

Inventories

For comprehensive condition assessment a real estate object must be decomposed into building components. The inventories process group allows managing of what building components are present in the real estate object in what quantities.

Inspections

With a present inventory of building components, an inspector can now collect information on the present defects to this inventory. Both structured information such as choosing from a list of defects, and unstructured information, such as a generic comment on the defect are collected. The defect is further enhanced by adding images.

RE Suite is fully compliant with NEN2767 to automatically calculate the condition of the building component and subsequently the building based on the registered defects.

An inspector can immediately register an activity to mitigate the defects and/or their effects. This can be coarse-grained by merely selecting from an available list of activities or be fully specified with a start and end date, repetitive period and indicative costs.

Activities

Occasionally an inspector will mitigate a defect as it is being registered. A description of the work, time spent as well as an optional list of used materials can be registered in this process group.

Analyses

The analysis process group allows for various forms of data manipulation, structuring, and disclosure. Inventory and inspection data that was separated in various previously mentioned processes to support an easy and uncluttered inspection process can be combined into an overview across the whole portfolio. Sorting, filtering and aggregation functionalities offer insight into the data available. Data can also be exported into csv format to import and/or analyse it in external tools.

The maintenance plan process allows for the creation of a full multi-year maintenance plan (MYMP) based on the registered measures for one or more selected objects. Considered is the registered information, but also the intended exploitation strategy, available cost data, VAT percentages, etc. The MYMP is parameterised and displayed as a Gantt-chart. This chart is manipulable, for example by dragging measures to different years to spread out costs.

Reports

The reports process allows users to present (subsets of) data from previous processes in the form of human-readable Microsoft Word, Microsoft Excel and/or pdf documents. A user can choose from the available list of styled documents or specify their own content table layout. This process uses functionality otherwise isolated in RE Reports for ease of use. Reports can be saved and versioned, with final versions saved as pdf documents with the document population automatically.

For more information, see RE Report.

Configuration

The configuration process group allows for manipulation of base data, such as the full list of available building components, defects, activities, etc. It is intended for expert users with full authorisation and expertise to maintain the data population.

3.1.4 RE IoT

RE IoT connects to (live) sensors and actuators. It allows for enrichment of digital twins to improve modelling realism. The resulting datasets can be used for analysis purposes or exported for external analysis.

RE IoT allows asset managers to maintain a population of devices, typically sensors and actuators. These devices can be linked to real estate objects. Data from these devices can be visualised directly in RE Suite and is downloaded on demand.

While RE IoT can be used for limited data warehousing purposes, this is not used in the REINCARNATE project. Instead, the role is fulfilled by Mainflux.

Figure 6: RE IoT

3.1.5 RE BIM

RE BIM unlocks Building Information Models and two-way interaction of both automation and human variety. IFC files can be opened as is or uploaded to the document population and linked to a real estate object for use elsewhere in the software.

Upon opening an IFC file the working area will display a 3D rendering of the BIM-model. A user can pan by dragging the model while holding the left mouse button. A user can rotate by dragging the model while holding the right mouse button. A user can zoom in and out by using the mouse wheel. Right-clicking in the viewport offers a menu with options, such as those to quickly show/hide whole sets of elements by type.

In the object navigator a tree shows the decomposition of the IFC model into elements. Selecting a node in the tree will highlight the corresponding element in the rendering and vice versa. Below the tree of elements in the object navigator a second tree of properties shows the available attributes for the selected node in the IFC-model.

Figure 7:RE BIM

3.1.6 RE Report

RE Report allows users to generate a variety of documents with the push of a button to report on workflows, processes, or events.

Standard reports flesh out predefined templates with data collected in other modules of the RE Suite. This produces professional documents in either Microsoft Word, or PDF format. To generate standard report, first select a type, then select the intended content from the object navigator and finally fill out any optional parameters. Click the 'generate report' button to produce a document.

Some reports are editable in-place. Elements that are otherwise manipulable through free text-entry elsewhere in the RE Suite can be filled out directly in a split-pane view.

Generic reports are fully customisable spreadsheets where a user can mix and order from a set of available columns and values. Use the panels below to drag and drop columns to and from the report using the left mouse button. Unlike standard reports, users can create their own templates. Generation works similarly to standard reports: select a template from the list, select content in the object navigator and click 'generate report'.

Figure 8: RE Report

3.1.7 RE OnSite

The mobile app RE OnSite allows for on-site data collection. Because it is fully part of the RE Suite, any and all data collected will be useable by the parent application. For example, the OnSite Condition Assessment module within RE OnSite seamlessly integrates with RE Maintenance.

In general, the app offers a similar user experience to the cloud application. A process navigator on the left-hand side hosts available processes. To its right an object navigator shows objects relevant for the currently selected process. On the right hand side, a working area allows for interaction on and with said objects.

RE OnSite Condition Assessment offers similar functionality to RE Maintenance but tailored for on-site use. Focus lies on objective and efficient data collection, supported by photos and other observations during the survey.

Figure 9: RE OnSite

3.1.8 Security and privacy

Privacy and security are of the utmost importance in any software application. The RE Suite both hosts and exposes data in human and machine-readable formats and could as such be vulnerable to exploitation resulting in data leaks. To mitigate this a number of measures are implemented, such that the RE Suite is fully compliant with the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR).

Firstly, all warehoused data is stored in data stores sandboxed for the REINCARNATE project. Strict Identity and Access Management (IAM) prevents data access from unauthorised users either within or from outside the REINCARNATE project.

Internal servers are members of a Virtual Private Network (VPN) and isolated from external communication with a firewall. Data exchange over the internet to end-users or non-member machines (such as tablets) occurs through firewalled gateway and over HTTPS. The connection is end-to-end encrypted using Transport Layer Security (TLS) and signed through a trusted certificate authority.

Within the RE Suite role assignment allows for authorisations to specific processes. As such functionality is only accessible to individual users with explicit permission.

3.2. Mainflux IoT Platform

Mainflux is open source IoT platform (Apache 2.0 license) with the complete full-scale capabilities for the development of Internet of Things solutions, IoT applications and smart connected products. Built as a set of microservices containerized by Docker and orchestrated with Kubernetes, it serves as software infrastructure and middleware which provides data aggregation/collection and management, data storage and connectivity management, event management, device management, and digital twin and application enablement.

Mainflux technologies and features are outlined below:

- Microservice Architecture
- Golang and Go Kit
- NginX
- TLS/DTLS Termination
- Reverse Proxy for UI
- Security Mutual TLS Authentication with X.509 Certificates
- Client-to-server authentication using client-side X.509
- Storage
 - SQL database for structured data
 - NoSQL database for Telemetry:
 - InfluxDB
 - MongoDB
- Messaging with supported protocols (connectors)
 - HTTP
 - MQTT
 - WS
 - CoAP
 - LoRaWAN
 - and standards: JSON, JWT 14 and SenML
- System provisioning
 - Provisioning things, where things represent devices or applications connected to the platform.
 - Provisioning channels, where channels represent communication pathways between devices and/or applications.
- Deployment:
 - Native
 - Docker containers (compose provided)
 - Kubernetes scripts

Mainflux Scales from PRi class devices to multi-datacenter with Kubernetes and Cassandra DB.

Figure 10: Mainflux IoT Platform Architecture

3.2.1 Mainflux IoT Platform entities

Mainflux open source IoT Platform consists of the following basic entities

Things, Channels, Users and Groups.

Things

The thing represents any data source or producer (provider), on the sides of the device like any kind of sensors or gateway as well as data receivers/consumers like actuators. The thing also can be a cloud-based app, or an edge-located app such as machine software, gateways, and visualization tools such as Grafana - that similarly can send or receive/consume data.

Channels

Channels are data communication pathways, that can be understood as pipes that define connectivity and how data flow from things (devices or applications) in both

directions a) sending messages to and b) receiving messages, using some of the provided communication protocols and storage systems.

A protocol is a set of rules that facilitates communication (i.e., data exchange) between separate machines/devices/applications in a network environment. The concept is analogous to the languages we use to communicate. Connectivity alone is not sufficient for devices and applications to communicate. It is necessary for them to communicate using the same "language." If two persons don't speak the same language, the interaction between them will be ineffective.

Users

Users are IoT Platform tenants and can represent physical persons and organizations, established via e-mail and password. Users can have different roles for secure access to and managing resources i.e. things and channels in "create, read, update, and delete (CRUD)" manner and define access control policies by connecting them.

Groups

For grouping Mainflux entities there are groups object in the auth service. Grouping of entities can be done for things and users but additionally, you can use groups for grouping some external entities as well. Groups can have parents and children. This opens the possibility and needs for complex queries of users, things and channels along the lines of metadata and hierarchical structure.

3.2.2 Mainflux IoT Platform Graphic User Interface (GUI) Manual

Mainflux IoT Platform is located at: <http://mainflux.eu.org>

The login screen that will appear requires standard user credentials.

Figure 11: Mainflux GUI - Home

After you have successfully logged in, the dashboard is displayed. The description and a few relevant links, including one that points to this documentation, are in the panel's center.

You can see the top-level selections in the menu on the right. Most of these choices correspond to Mainflux entities and allow you to manage those entities in a "CRUD" create, read, update, and delete manner.

Users

As explained before, Users can be physical persons or organizations.

The first screen of this section presents users with their email and associated ID.

Figure 12: Mainflux GUI -Users menu

To create and invite a new User, simply click on the + Create button. The box for entering a new User's email and password will appear, with Create button.

Figure 13: Mainflux GUI – Creating a User

In order to see all details about the User click on the detail's icon (three vertical dots). Except for User email and ID, an additional Membership box for the Groups to which Users is assigned will also appear on the screen.

The box presents the current membership, as well drop menu with all Created Groups as well associated Assign button.

Figure 14: Mainflux GUI – User details

Groups

Groups serve for grouping Users, Things but also some external entities. On the first screen, again with the + Create button, you can create a Group with its name, type, and description.

Figure 15: Mainflux GUI – Groups menu

Figure 16: Mainflux GUI – Creating a Group

On the details for the particular Group, (three vertical dots icon) three boxes are present. User Group Info, which provides the given name and description of the group, its automatically created ID, and Owner ID, i.e., ID of the User who created the group (in this screen it is admin@example.com).

Also, for assigning, the User to desired Group, the check box next to User and the Assign button should be used.

Figure 17: Mainflux GUI – Assigning User to a Group

Things

You will be presented with the following screen in response to your selection of the Things menu option: This is a list of the things that are associated with you as user, ie. the person that is signed in.

Figure 18: Mainflux GUI – Things menu

To create a new thing, you must first click the plus sign, then type the things name, and finally click the check mark sign:

Figure 19: Mainflux GUI - Creating a Thing

The Thing's ID will be generated automatically.

You may now view the specifics of your Thing by selecting the details icon (three vertical dots) and clicking on it. You will then be taken to the screen that displays the details.

The thing's ID and Key are displayed on the details screen. The first is the unique internal identifier for the Mainflux. The second should be understood as the Things password. You will not be able to send or receive messages with Thing until you have its ID and Key.

Figure 20: Mainflux GUI – Things Key and ID

The Things Key abstracts away complexities of different protocol authorization procedures in Mainflux.

In the same mode, as Things abstract away the complexity of protocol authorization, Channels abstract away the complexities of creating protocol message pathways ("communication pipes"). To communicate and exchange data messages with a Thing, we always have first to connect that Thing to the appropriate channel.

The drop-down menu that contains all the available channels may be found in the top-right corner.

Figure 21: Mainflux GUI – Channels drop-down menu for connecting Things

In this example, the channel represents the communication pathway for example a particular machine in the factory.

Figure 22: Mainflux GUI – Example of a Thing connected to a Channel

If this machine is equipped with numerous sensors, which are represented by Mainflux things, then all these sensors communicate with a Mainflux IoT Platform through a single channel.

For example, this single channel may represent (and abstract away) an MQTT host and topic. To connect Thing to a Channel, select the channels and click the connect button. Here the Things metadata can be also changed. A Thing can have arbitrary data added to it using Metadata. In most cases, we will include a type of Thing. A type may, for instance, refer to a device or an application. More specific types, such as CNC milling machines and the like could be also added.

This kind of data is referred to as Metadata because, in contrast to thing's key and thing's ID, which are Mainflux internal data required for its efficient functioning, Mainflux does not comprehend anything about the structure or semantics of metadata. It is the responsibility of the user to understand how the metadata is structured and what it means, whether that user is a real person or another application that is built on top of Mainflux.

To add a new segment of metadata, simply enter a valid JSON object into the Metadata card and then click on the edit button. You will receive a signal that your metadata modification was successful if the JSON you sent is correct, which is something you may check in advance, for example, here:

The screenshot displays the Mainflux v0.13.2 interface. On the left is a navigation sidebar with 'Things' selected. The main area is divided into three panels:

- Thing Info:** Name: Fluke 3561 Vibration, ID: 3fbe1e84-ab93-43be-83be-014a4644ce31, Key: aaf0e330-f3ca-47ea-8c80-c98c28d86b9c, Connections: 2.
- Connections (2):** A table with columns 'Name' and 'Channel ID'.

Name	Channel ID	
chan1	bfb5943f-4aad-45a4-9196-b3fce5903227	<input type="checkbox"/>
Extruder Machines Vibration	03014df8-0be6-44f9-8822-761e039794dc	<input type="checkbox"/>
- Metadata:** A text area containing a JSON object:

```
1 {
2   "mfkey": {
3     "mfkey1": "mfkey1"
4   },
5   "type": "Vibration monitoring sensor"
6 }
```

 A 'Save' button is visible to the right.

Figure 23: Mainflux GUI – Metadata associated with a particular Channel

Finally, you may view all the messages that have been sent or received by the current Thing in the card Messages:

Figure 24: Mainflux GUI – Messages sent by particular Thing and their formats

By clicking on the table dropdown menu and selecting JSON from the available options, you can obtain a list of "raw" messages, which are messages formatted in the form of a list of JSON objects. To distinguish whether Thing is a receiver or a sender of a message, simply compare the publisher field of a certain message with the Thing's ID. If they are the same, then the current Thing is the publisher of the message.

Figure 25: Mainflux GUI – Things ID as info whether Thing is message receiver or sender

Channels

Similar logic applies to the interface part for CRUD operations on Channels as it does to the interface part for Things. First, by simply clicking on Channels on the left side of the menu, you can view a list of the channels to which you (or your user) have access.

Figure 26: Mainflux GUI – Channels menu

The new Channel can then be created in the same manner as a new Thing from that point forward. Simply click the plus symbol, type the name of the channel, and then click the checkbox.

Figure 27: Mainflux GUI – Creating a Channel

You can access the channel details page by clicking on the three-points button. The Ashvin IoT platform enables one-to-one, one-to-many, many-to-one, and many-to-many connections between arbitrary objects and channels. In other words, you can link anything to any Channel, as well as the other way around. You can connect Things and Channels either on the Thing's details page or on Channel's details page. The procedure is the same, on the right side are available devices i.e., Things.

Figure 28: Mainflux GUI – Connecting a Channel with a Thing

You can edit the metadata of a Channel in the same way that you edit the metadata of other Things. Simply click the Edit button after entering a valid JSON. If the JSON object is valid, you will get a success notification:

Figure 29: Mainflux GUI – Channel metadata

Similar to Things, metadata does not have any connection to the inner workings of the Mainflux IoT platform. Rather, it enables designers of IoT systems to create an IoT data system with semantics and structure of their own choosing.

3.2.3 Data privacy and security

Privacy and cybersecurity are two of the most important problems for industries that are becoming increasingly digitized. Cyberattacks are getting more complicated, and fiercer at the same time, while the number of industries that are the target of these attacks is growing. Furthermore, the Internet of Things and digital twin technologies introduce a new set of challenges, risks and privacy concerns.

Although privacy and cybersecurity are intertwined, privacy incorporates a wider range of rights than cybersecurity, including those outlined in the European Charter of Fundamental Rights. These rights include safeguarding personal data and the right to access information. In today's situations, protecting one's privacy is almost always directly linked to one's level of compliance with the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR).

As explained before, the role of the Mainflux open-source IoT Platform within CP-IM is to provide real-time data communication pipelines from physical data sources (such as devices, sensors, and actuators) and virtual data sources (generally, in the cloud or on-

premises applications that gather or generate data). It also must perform the function of a centralized location for the storing and retrieval of data in a secure manner in order to fulfil the data requirements of the Digital Twin platform as well as other CP-IM segments.

A unified option for granting exclusive access to all systems inside the Mainflux platform as well as unified management of platform users was also necessary. In this regard, security measures and procedures must be implemented to prevent unwanted and unauthorized data and communication pipelines access and eavesdropping.

In conclusion, the communication pipelines require a centralized point of access, as well as a uniform method of data retrieval, which must be accessible from both the outside and the inside of the IoT Platform.

In that sense, the Mainflux IoT Platform is highly secure covering these three points: communication pipeline topology, secure access and retrieval of data, and a uniform point and means of data access.

All connections are encrypted via TLS v1.3 and with mutual TLS client-side X.509 certificates - currently representing the highest industry standard.

TLS or Transport Layer Security is an encryption protocol that encrypts messages and authenticates communication parties. As previously explained, the protocol is a set of rules and procedures on how the exchanged data is formatted and interpreted. While encryption is a process of transforming a message into secret code to hide the encrypted information. This means that TLS is a set of rules for message encryption, transmission, and decryption. TLS ensures client-server authentication, which is the process of establishing whether a client or a server is who or what it claims to be. Authentication is ensured using Transport Layer Security (TLS). This in the end results that Users and Things can establish a secure connection over the IoT network. By default, the TLS protocol only uses X.509 certificates to verify the identity of the server to the client; the application layer oversees authenticating the client to the server. Using client-side X.509 authentication, TLS also provides client-to-server authentication.

Furthermore, Mainflux uses mTLS (mutual TLS), an extension of TLS, which is basically a TLS with a two-way verification, adding an additional level of security.

The purpose of implementing data encryption in Mainflux is to protect the network from the various cyber-attacks that are now in use. Man-in-the-middle attacks can be mitigated via mutual authentication, which ensures that no third parties are interfering between the sender and the receiver of the message. Since mutual authentication checks timestamps and ends sessions if a certain time delay is exceeded, this also protects against replay attacks.

After the certificates have been exchanged and validated, at which point we will have established that the parties involved in the communication are, in fact, whom they say they are, we are in a position to determine the access privileges that are held by the party that corresponds to them.

For that purpose, Mainflux uses Single Sign-on (SSO) authentication methods. This technology is part of Identity and Access Management (IAM) and enables the management of electronic or digital identities and network access rights for individuals, hardware, and applications.

User management services, directory services, and authentication and authorization services make up its most crucial parts. SSO with two-factor authentication is selected since current cybersecurity best practices recommend against the practice in which users generate and remember numerous passwords because this frequently leads to password simplification, which introduces vulnerability. Additionally, two-factor authentication safeguards the Mainflux IoT platform from weaknesses brought on by poor management of passwords offline and online (phishing attacks) (writing the password on paper). SSO enables users to use one set of login credentials (e.g., a username and password) to access multiple applications and websites. In the context of CP-IM, when a user logs in to the IoT platform he will be automatically authenticated to other modules and instances, i.e to RE Suite, Digital Twin platform, Circular Potential Prediction Module, etc.

Strong single sign-on (SSO) and authentication procedures protect against identity attacks such as spoofing attacks and impersonation attacks.

4. Implementation

4.1. Launch version

In the launch version of the CP-IM RE Suite and Mainflux come together for the first time. Both components have distinct roles in the platform. Users interact with the Mainflux platform for ‘thing’ and ‘channel’ management, managing their population of sensors and actuators.

Users interact with the RE Suite for a variety of workflows, among which are portfolio management, condition assessment and circular potential analysis.

4.2. Architecture

IoT devices interact with the Mainflux platform directly as ‘things’ communicating via ‘Channels’. The Mainflux platform is responsible for hosting sensor data in its isolated database.

RE Suite communicates with the Mainflux platform through its REST API. RE Suite hosts real estate object information in its own isolated database. RE Suite can communicate with external systems such as external data stores.

Figure 30: CP-IM architecture

5. Future work

The launch version of the CP-IM platform is a major milestone. It integrates existing software components in the form of Mainflux and RE Suite into an information management platform. Beyond the launch version, however, the domain of circular potential can and should be further explored.

Firstly, where both Mainflux and RE Suite have internal data management structures based on relevant standards, no use is made of any common ontology. Such an ontology aimed at the circularity potential domain will be developed within REINCARNATE WP1. The CP-IM can and should evolve to connect and make use of such an ontology.

Secondly, where the architecture is prepared for connections with external systems, these can and should be developed further. Candidates include, but are not limited to:

- Madaster¹ and other material and product data sources
- Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) systems
- Cost information data sources
- BIM-servers
- Geographical Information Systems (GIS)

Thirdly, approaching consortium partners as representatives of end users in the application domain should lead to functional requirements elicitation. With the CP-IM publicly available for use within the REINCARNATE project, an inventory of improvements and new wishes can lead to strong improvements in the CP-IM and realistic exploitable results.

¹ <https://madaster.nl>